

were often obtained, but were too much complicated to be analyzed. More intensive studies are needed in each country, using adult plants and sophisticated techniques. ❧

Pathogenic strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* and related resistant and susceptible rice varieties in Korea

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Two phage-type strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* were identified in Korea by the use of four different bacteriophages, in 1968, and seven had been identified by 1971. The seven strains were categorized according to virulence into three groups, but the groups were not called pathotypes or races.

By 1976, five groups of pathotypes were recognized in Korea. To classify the isolates, they were inoculated to four groups of differential varieties. Of 67 isolates collected from limited areas of the country, 22 belonged to pathotype I, 8 to pathotype II, 2 to III, 5 to IV, and 30 to V.

Pathotype I attacks only Kinmaze-group varieties including IRI 323, 326, 327, 330, Milyang 21, 23, 28, 34, Suweon 264, 265, 267, 268, 271, Jinheung, and Glutinous Tong-il. Pathotype II attacks, in addition to those varieties, Kokyoku-group varieties such as Iri 319, 328, Milyang 25, and Suweon 263. Pathotype III attacks all varietal groups except the Wase-Aikoku group varieties (Milyang 30), and pathotype IV attacks all the varieties tested. Pathotype V attacks varieties of the Kinmaze and Wase-Aikoku groups.

During the 1976 growing season, severe epidemics of kresiek disease occurred in areas where the new variety Milyang 23 had been introduced. It was the first time that kresiek was officially reported in Korea. Of all cultivars used in studies of kresiek, Milyang 23 showed the most susceptible reactions to all five pathotypes. The relationship between pathotypes and kresiek symptoms was not clearly proved, although it seemed to be affected by inoculum concentrations, inoculation sites, and varietal differences. ❧

Pathogenic strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the Philippines

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The virulence patterns of *X. oryzae* isolates collected in the Philippines from 1963 to 1976 were evaluated on four host varieties: IR8, which has shown no genes for resistance to bacterial blight; IR20, which has the dominant gene *Xa 4*; IR1545-339, which carries the recessive gene *xa 5*; and DV85, which has one recessive gene similar to *xa 5* and a dominant gene that is different from *Xa 4*.

Pathogenic strains or races clearly exist in the population of *X. oryzae* in the Philippines. Most of the 83 isolates belong to one group that we call the common strain, exemplified by isolate PXO 61. Host genotypes carrying either of the two major genes (*Xa 4* or *xa 5*) are resistant to that strain. The Isabela strain is exemplified by the isolate PXO 79 collected in Davao; the host genotype carrying the recessive gene *xa 5*

is resistant. The third group of isolates, which makes up a small portion of the present collection and is typified by PXO 71 from the Palawan area, overcomes the resistance of host genotypes that carry both the dominant and recessive genes. It appears that PXO 71 is more compatible with genotypes with *xa 5* than with those with *Xa 4*. It always produces more lesions on IR1545-339 than on IR20. DV85 is resistant to all isolates. A variety like IR8, with no apparent genes for resistance to bacterial blight, is susceptible to the three groups of isolates. All isolates under study produced lesions on IR8, but isolates such as PXO 10 that have weak virulence produced considerably fewer lesions.

The results also confirmed that isolates compatible with a certain host genotype are present in an area before the particular host genotype is widely planted. PXO 71 is one of the isolates found in Palawan in 1974; some isolates of the Isabela strain were collected in Davao in 1963. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Eriophyid mite appears on rice in Thailand

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The 4-legged eriophyid mites are quite uncommon on rice. In Keifer's 1967 index, only one rice-infesting species is given — *Eriophyes bakkeri* Keifer, which was described from Africa. Another species — *Cheiracus sulcatus* Keifer — has been found in Thailand. I encountered it on the undersides of mature blades in paddy at Ban Pa Ha, Chiang Rai Province, North Thailand.

The infestation was heavy, but it occurred on old leaves blemished by other agents. It would therefore be premature, on the basis of visual inspection only, to attribute damage to the mite. The mite has to be evaluated under controlled conditions. ❧

Grasshoppers on rice in Pakistan

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Rice suffers considerable loss due to grasshopper attack in Pakistan. The important species are *Heroglyphus banian* (F.) and *Oxya multidentata* Will. *H. banian*, earlier reported as a Serious pest in the plains, currently occurs mostly in hilly areas. Intensive cultivation in the Plains may be responsible for the destruction of egg pods there. Abundance of *H. banian* in the hills may be due to favorable climate or undisturbed oviposition sites. *O. multidentata* is found all over Pakistan but is more abundant in hilly areas. *Oxya velox* (F.), a serious pest in almost all rice-growing countries, is of minor significance here. It is found only in the hills and foothills. *Acrida exaltata* Wlk.,

Acrida sp., *Acrotylus humbertianus* Sauss, *Atractomorpha acutipennis* (Guer.), *Calliptamus* sp., *Catantops pinguis* Stal., *Chroedicus illustris* Wlk., *Eyprepocnemis plorans* Charp, *Shirakiacris shirakii* I. Bol., *Oedaleus abruptus* Thunb., and *Truxalis grandis* Dirsh are also found on rice but in low numbers.

Grasshoppers are more serious in the rice nurseries where young nymphs accumulate in large numbers and damage the seedlings. In some cases almost the whole of a nursery plot is destroyed. Plowing of fields and digging of embankments during winter seem good control measures because they destroy most of the egg pods. ❧

Insecticidal control of the brown planthopper in the field

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Field studies on the efficacy of insecticides against the rice brown

planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* showed that the maximum reduction of insect numbers occurred in plots treated with carbofuran 3% G (2.25 kg a.i./ha), followed by that in plots treated with methamidophos (0.1% spray), Phorate (2.25 kg a.i./ha), and phoxim (0.05% spray). In general, mephosfolan 10% G was found to be ineffective. ❧

Effect of paddy-water and foliar applications of insecticides on brown planthopper populations 9–12 weeks after transplanting, Annamalaiagar, India, kuruvai, 1973.

Treatment ^a	Application rate (kg a.i./ha)	Planthoppers ^b (no./hill)					Change from control level (%)
		9 wk	10 wk	11 wk	12 wk	Mean	
Carbofuran granules	0.75	0	61	27	28	29	- 67
	1.50	0	0	0	44	11	- 88
	2.25	0	0	0	0	0	- 100
Phorate granules	0.75	5	39	121	143	77	- 13
	1.50	6	33	153	156	87	- 2
	2.25	3	13	62	71	37	- 58
Mephosfolan granules	0.75	2	58	160	128	87	- 2
	1.50	3	132	123	125	96	+ 8
	2.25	4	20	122	122	92	+ 4
Methamidophos spray	0.025%	3	17	62	61	41	- 54
	0.05%	4	2	111	88	51	- 42
	0.1%	7	18	46	76	37	- 58
Phoxim spray	0.025%	4	37	128	131	73	- 17
	0.05%	2	45	78	76	50	- 43
	0.1%	4	77	99	92	68	- 23
Control	-	13	48	132	143	89

^aChemicals applied on 15th and 45th days after transplanting; treatments significant at 1% level (C.D. = 1.741).

^bAv. of 20 hills.

Research on pests of rice in Malawi (Central Africa)

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From 1971 until 1975 a research project was conducted to determine the relative importance of various insect pests of rice in Malawi.

The most numerous insect pest of rice is the stem borer *Diopsis thoracica* Westwood (Diptera; Diopsidae). Other diopsids are unimportant. Lepidopterous

stem borers, such as *Maliarpha separatella* Rag., *Chilo partellus* (Swinh.), *Chilo diffusilineus* (de Joannis), *Sesamia calamistas* (Hamps.), *Schoenobius* sp., and *Thopeutis* spp., are of little importance, since they are controlled by many parasitoids. At the end of prolonged rainy seasons, fields planted late were attacked by the rice gall midge *Orseola oryzae* (Wood-Mason).

Three larval parasitoids kept that pest under control. Several outbreaks of the rice beetle *Trichispa sericea* (Guer.), occurred in rice fields with high water

levels. In the 1972–73 season several hectares of nurseries were destroyed by this species. However, parasitoids usually kept the beetle under control. Other pests of minor importance were lepidopterous defoliators such as *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guen.), *Spodoptera cilium* Guen., *Diacrisia scortillum* (Wllgr.), *Borbo borbonica* (Boisd.), *Grammodes geometrica* F., *Mythimna* sp. and *Brachmia* sp., the green rice bug *Nezara viridula* (L.), and the mole cricket *Gryllotalpa africana* (P. de Beauv.).

Most of the Lepidoptera were identified by Dr. P. E. S. Whalley and Dr. I. W. B. Nye of the British Museum (Natural History).

The project formed part of the Lake Chilwa Coordinated Research Project and was financed by the Netherlands Foundation for the Advancement of Tropical Research (WOTRO), and the Research Council of the University of Malawi. ❧

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Weed competition in transplanted rice

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To study the effect of various weeds in season-long competition with IR34, the desired weed species were sown with the rice at transplanting. Then at regular intervals all weeds, except the species under study, were removed.

All weeds except *Salvinia natans* caused yield losses (see table). The losses ranged from 19% (with competition from *Marsilea minuta*) to 43% (with competition from *Fimbristylis* sp. and *Echinochloa colona*). Losses were greater when competition was from more than one weed. The greatest loss (55%) occurred in the unweeded check plot, where all the tested weed species and the natural weed population competed simultaneously against rice.